

A Review of the Applicability of the ASTERIX Protocol on Passive Radar Systems

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Abstract—*ASTERIX enjoys widespread adoption by radar networks, air traffic control, and cooperative identification systems. The protocol is evolving over time, with the addition of new message classes, called categories. Recently, it has been expanded to include two new categories, CAT. 015 and 016, in an attempt to better accommodate passive radars and multistatic systems in general. In this paper, we evaluate the suitability of the ASTERIX protocol for the transfer of target information originating from passive radars. The evaluation is based on the identification of the most suitable information level to be shared, and the corresponding selection of the information that needs to be exchanged at that level. A one-to-one correspondence between the selected information and the protocol's data items is established and reported. Finally, there is a flip side to this paper. It can serve as a guide on how to use ASTERIX for passive radar data transmission.*

Keywords— *ASTERIX, passive radar, system integration, communication interface, JDL levels*

I. INTRODUCTION

Today's network-centric warfare paradigm places increasing emphasis on the effective integration and fusion of information across heterogeneous sensing assets to support the creation of a unified operational picture, and the efficient deployment, management, and utilization of resources. Within this context, Passive Radar (PR) systems stand to benefit significantly from robust integration frameworks and data fusion mechanisms, given their role as gap-filler solutions and the unique nature and challenges of their operation.

Individual passive radar sensors typically exhibit coarser localization accuracy than active radars, a consequence of their moderate antenna azimuth resolution, low signal-to-noise ratios, and bistatic geometries that constrain precise target position estimation. By enabling the fusion of detections originating from multiple passive radar systems, or between passive radar and heterogeneous sensors such as radio range finders or optical systems, it becomes possible to improve overall localization performance and target detection capability while maintaining the inherent covertness of PR

operations. Multi-sensor fusion has been shown to reduce uncertainty, enhance track continuity, and mitigate geometry-imposed limitations that single passive sensors cannot overcome alone. To support such capabilities, an interface for sharing target detections from passive radars is needed.

ASTERIX is a standard for exchanging air traffic surveillance data. Since its appearance in 1984, it has evolved to become the de facto standard for civil and military radar data exchange [1]. ASTERIX classifies the data to be exchanged into various categories, which define the structure and usage of the corresponding messages. Over the lifespan of the standard, the number of distinct categories has increased from 2 to 64. These additions are driven by the need to accommodate new sensor types or improve existing information representation capabilities.

ASTERIX categories 015 [2] and 016 [3] have been added to the standard to address the need for the transmission of independent non-cooperative surveillance (INCS) system target reports and have been selected by the recent ED-288 technical specification [4]. INCS system types include monostatic, bistatic, multi-static (active and/or passive), and even electro-optic sensors. Category 015 includes a 'hook' to category 016 that enables traceability to further information, detailing the configuration of the sensor. Such information can include the location of the sensors, receivers, and the location and the nature of any opportunity transmitters that were used to support the detection, e.g., FM, DAB, and/or DVB-T.

The evaluation of categories 015 & 016 for representing target information originating from passive radar systems is the main topic of this paper. The relevant literature today only covers a protocol usage example [5]. The evaluation is based on a generic PR system architecture presented in section 2 and the ability to transfer the required information as defined in section 3. The actual mapping of target information to ASTERIX message data items is conducted in section 4, section 5 discusses how the proposed interface can enable data fusion, and finally, in section 6, the paper concludes with a

summary of the evaluation results and future research directions in the field of radar data exchange.

Fig. 1. Passive Radar System architecture made up from bistatic pairs, a communication interface and a processing system.

II. PASSIVE RADAR SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

PR systems exploit opportunistic radio emissions for target illumination. Each receiver–illuminator pair, called a bistatic pair, is subject to standalone signal processing that yields an ellipsoid of possible target locations. If the PR system is capable of target echo angle of arrival (AoA) estimation, a single bistatic pair can perform target detection and localization. As such, a bistatic pair represents the primitive building block of passive radar systems. It is typical for passive radars to form multiple bistatic pairs to perform target localization using multilateration. In the case of multistatic systems, there can be multiple receivers, leading to a geographically distributed collection of bistatic pairs.

While inter-system information exchange is the primary process that comes to mind when thinking of communication protocols and standards, it is evident that intra-system information exchange is required as well. Every PR system can be viewed as a collection of single-channel receiver-transmitter bistatic pairs outputting information that need to be combined to form the final target detection.

By using a common interface for the sharing of the information originating from every single-channel receiver-transmitter bistatic pair, either inside the same system or between different systems, an abstraction layer is created, enabling unified processing, scalability, and system homogenization. The architecture of such a system is presented in Fig. 1. Note that there can be multiple processing units, either within the radar systems themselves, to render

them self-contained solutions or to perform centralized processing as part of a distributed sensor network.

We identify the primary task of categories 015 and 016 to be the accommodation of the needs of the communication interfaces depicted in Fig. 1. Depending on the PR system capabilities, the communication interface may have to carry bistatic measurements or WGS84 target locations. The target information after the overall processing is completed is more easily represented by existing categories due to being complete detections similar to the ones produced by monostatic radars. It can use the same categories as the ones used for the bistatic pair measurements or category 048 by emulating a monostatic radar if no measurement metadata (standard deviations, covariances, etc.) are required.

III. INFORMATION TO BE SHARED

The principal quantities measured by a passive radar are bistatic range, bistatic Doppler shift, and, when available, AoA. For each detected target, one such measurement triplet can be produced per bistatic pair. For any practical purpose, bistatic velocity is preferred instead of bistatic Doppler shift. Clutter suppression, target classification or target tracking through the use of kinematic models use velocity, not Doppler shift. The two are related through the following formula:

$$V_b = \lambda \cdot f_d \quad (1)$$

where λ is the carrier wavelength, f_d is the bistatic Doppler shift, and V_b is the bistatic velocity. The conversion of bistatic Doppler shift to bistatic velocity is straight forward and feasible even for reduced capability systems. Therefore, bistatic velocity and not bistatic Doppler shift is selected as the principal measurement quantity to be.

To render these measurements meaningful, they must be accompanied by information describing at least the positions of the corresponding illuminator of opportunity (IoO) and receiver composing the bistatic pair. For systems employing data fusion and for operational usefulness purposes, additional metadata is required—such as measurement standard deviations, estimated resolutions, target classifications, SNR, etc. The specific parameters included depend on the fusion methodology; here, the selected quantities correspond to the needs of Kalman filter–based tracking, a well-established fusion technique in radar systems.

Table I lists the complete set of raw measurements and associated metadata that the PR interface may transfer. Depending on system capabilities and complexity, only a subset may be available. The list is intentionally designed to be generic, allowing radio direction finders or optronic systems to be represented through azimuth and elevation fields. In case a transmitter or receiver is part of more than one bistatic pairs the related information does not have to be transmitted multiple times. Table I is not a message format and the actual receiver/transmitter information are carried by a separate message that is associated with the bistatic measurement message with a 16 bit identifier. Therefore, only the identifiers are repeated. The purpose column provides a description of the intended use of each piece of information.

TABLE I. SELECTED DATA TO BE SHARED THROUGH THE PR COMMUNICATION INTERFACE

Measured Quantity	Units	Purpose
Bistatic Range	Meters	Target localization
Range resolution	Meters	Localization reference accuracy
Range std	Meters	Localization accuracy
Bistatic Velocity	m/s	Target speed estimation – Clutter filtering - Tracking
Bistatic Velocity resolution	m/s	Target speed reference resolution
Bistatic Velocity std	m/s	Target speed accuracy
Azimuth Angle	Degrees from true North	2D Target localization
Azimuth resolution	Degrees	Localization reference accuracy
Azimuth std	Degrees	Localization accuracy
Elevation	Degrees from horizontal plane	3D Target localization
Elevation Resolution	Degrees	Localization reference accuracy
Elevation std	Degrees	Localization accuracy
Tx location	WGS84 coordinates	Transmitter location
Rx location	WGS84 coordinates	Receiver location
Carrier Wavelength	m	Target speed estimation
Direct Path Power	dBm	Target RCS estimation
Reflected Path Power	dBm	Target RCS estimation
Target SNR	dB	Detection confidence
Target Class	String enumerate	Target classification
Time between measurements	seconds	Tracking – Data fusion
Target Location	WGS84 coordinates	Target localization
Target Velocity	m/s	Target speed - Tracking
Covariance Matrices	multiple	Fusion - Tracking

Among the measured quantities, perhaps the wavelength and the direct and reflected path powers require the most explanation. Monostatic radars are able to determine the radar cross section (RCS) of a target by measuring the ratio of the reflected to transmitted power and compensating for the path losses. Due to their monostatic geometry, path losses are far easier to account for than in PR systems with bistatic geometries. Target RCS is used for size estimation and tracking. The transmission of the direct and reflected path powers enables other components to apply sophisticated path loss models (APM [6], ITM [7]) and estimate the target RCS.

There is also the question of whether the data shared should correspond to target tracks or plots. A target plot represents a single, instantaneous detection. A target track is a time-correlated sequence of plots. Producing target tracks requires the PR system to apply a tracker to correlate different target plots over time. The sensor detecting the target is most

of the time better suited to perform tracking. Access to the raw data makes possible the use of advanced tracking techniques that do not rely solely on a kinematic model but also use target features like the micro Doppler signature and target reflectivity to associate successive detections. However, the application of advanced tracking techniques increases the sensor complexity. Since there is a trade-off between sensor complexity and capability, the decision for the specified interface is to accommodate both sensor types. Sensors that do not perform target tracking can generate target plots and delegate tracking to another system if needed.

It should be noted that some measured quantities of Table I are redundant. An example is the bistatic range and the target position. A sophisticated sensor, in our case a PR system that exploits multiple illuminators of opportunity or has AoA measurement capability, can determine the target location directly and thus can avoid outputting low-level measurements like the bistatic range. We have included both to cover all system types.

IV. ASTERIX APPLICABILITY

This section describes the categories selected for use by the passive radar system and maps the information in Table I to ASTERIX data items. The three main categories that are applicable to the PR system are:

a) Category 015: Conveys target measurement information (plots/tracks) and is the single most important ASTERIX category when it comes to passive radar systems. It was created explicitly taking into account passive and active multistatic systems. It is able to transfer, in a standardized manner, both low-level bistatic related measurement information and high-level target information. The type of information supported is extensive, ranging from primary measurements to covariance matrices. Each message can be associated with one or more category 016 messages carrying information regarding the bistatic pairs contributing to the measurement.

b) Category 016: The principal purpose of this category is to provide additional configuration data of INCS systems. Information about the transmitters and receivers that contribute to target measurement plots/tracks enables the fusion of overlapping coverage data from multiple sensors and makes possible the 2D or 3D target localization through the aggregation of the necessary number of bistatic measurements. The transmitter and receiver configuration is dynamic since, as a target passes through the monitored airspace volume, the target may be illuminated by signals from different transmitters, and the signals emanating from the target may be received by different receivers. Key data items include the receiver and transmitter locations, their unique identifiers, and the pair identification.

c) Category 025: Every radar has to generate service and component status reports to notify other systems about its status and permit overall management. Service status has to do with the status of individual services that are provided by the system, while component status refers to the status of the various hardware components comprising the system. This category provides three types of reports: Service and System Status reports, Component Status reports, and Service Statistics reports. Consequently, it can cover the relevant needs of the PR system. We will not elaborate further about this category here due to its straightforward use. For more information, the reader can review [8].

The one-to-one correspondence between the data selected to be shared and the protocol data items that are suitable to represent them is presented in Table II. For some measured quantities, there is no direct mapping to standardized ASTERIX data items. Both cat. 015 and 016 permit the addition of special purpose fields, which are an extensibility mechanism incorporated into the protocol. The downside of using those is that they can compromise interoperability, and so their use must be kept at a minimum. Of the selected data to be shared, there are two with no direct mapping.

TABLE II. MAPPING OF PASSIVE RADAR TARGET INFORMATION TO ASTERIX DATA ITEMS

Measured Quantity	ASTERIX Category	ASTERIX data item
Bistatic Range	015	625 Subfield #1
Range resolution	015	625 Subfield #2
Range std	015	625 Subfield #3
Bistatic Velocity	015	626 Subfield #1 a
Bistatic Velocity resolution	015	no mapping
Bistatic Velocity std	015	626 Subfield #2 a
Azimuth Angle	015	627 Subfield #1
Azimuth resolution	015	627 Subfield #2
Azimuth std	015	627 Subfield #3
Elevation	015	628 Subfield #1
Elevation Resolution	015	628 Subfield #2
Elevation std	015	628 Subfield #3
Tx location	016	410
Rx location	016	420
Carrier Wavelength	016	no mapping
Direct Path Power	015	630 Subfield #1
Reflected Path Power	015	630 Subfield #3
Target SNR	015	630 Subfield #4
Target Class	015	300
Time between measurements	015	050
Target Location	015	600 Subfield #1
Target Velocity	015	602 Subfield #1
Covariance Matrices	015	626 Subfield #5
		602 Subfield #4

Bistatic velocity and bistatic velocity standard deviation are directly mapped to data item 015/626, an added reason for transferring velocity and not Doppler shift. Bistatic velocity resolution cannot be mapped to an existing data item, and since it depends on the bistatic angle [9] which is not always known, cannot be inferred. Together with the carrier wavelength are the two quantities that unavoidably have to be mapped to special purpose fields.

The applicability of the protocol must take into account its operational viability. Communication overhead has to be analyzed to make sure it can be met by existing networking technologies. ASTERIX is bit-oriented and thus more efficient than other protocols that use JSON or XML representations. PR systems, unlike traditional monostatic radars that output a single plot per target per scan, can generate up to $N \times M$ bistatic detections per target per scan, where N is the number of receivers and M the number of illuminators of opportunity. This is the limiting case for the data rate of the interfaces defined in this paper, since transmitting WGS84 target locations requires a single message. Using the standard

user application profile (UAP) for category 015 with the extension for the special purpose field needed for the bistatic Doppler shift resolution, 70 bytes per bistatic target detection are needed. To this value, an extra 28 bytes have to be added to account for the headers and checksums of the protocols (UDP/IPv4) used to transfer the message.

The desirable update rate of the generated reports depends on the target profile and operational considerations. In this analysis, we shall use the parameters derived from the second performance level (PL2) of the ED-288 technical specification [4]. The maximum update rate is 5 seconds, which coincides with the update rate for major terminal areas [10]. The resultant data rate is 157 bps per target per bistatic pair. With three bistatic pairs needed for 3D localization, tracking two hundred and fifty targets would require 120 kbps in total. These data rates can be accommodated by second-generation tactical data links [11] as well as by LEO communication constellations that have aggressively entered the military communications arena. The calculated data rates do not include the bandwidth required for category 016 and 025 messages. Those should be transmitted periodically, but the update rate is much lower in comparison with the bistatic plot messages.

V. DATA FUSION JDL MODEL MAPPING

The adoption of ASTERIX as a communication interface for passive radar systems directly supports multi-sensor data fusion architectures as formalized by the Joint Directors of Laboratories (JDL) data fusion model [12]. The JDL model categorizes fusion processes into hierarchical levels, ranging from signal-level processing to high-level situation and impact assessment. ASTERIX categories 015 and 016 primarily address the needs of JDL Levels 1 and 2, while indirectly enabling higher-level fusion functions.

JDL Level 1 fusion concerns the estimation and refinement of object states, including position, velocity, and associated uncertainties. Passive radar measurements, such as bistatic range, bistatic Doppler shift, and angle-of-arrival, naturally map to this level. The described communication interface supports the transmission of both plot-level and track-level information, making it suitable for Level 1 fusion across distributed passive radar systems. JDL Level 2 fusion focuses on the relationships between objects and their interpretation within a broader situational context. In passive radar systems, this includes target association across bistatic pairs, multi-sensor track correlation, and target classification refinement. ASTERIX category 015 provides data items that support classification and confidence estimation, enabling fusion nodes to combine kinematic information with non-kinematic attributes such as signal-to-noise ratio, reflected power, or target class hypotheses. By correlating multiple detections over time and across sensors, fusion systems can improve classification confidence and reduce false alarms.

Although ASTERIX does not directly encode intent or impact assessments, the information conveyed by CAT 015 and 016 provides the foundational inputs required for JDL Level 3 (Threat Refinement) and Level 4 (Process Refinement) functions. For example, consistent and accurate track information enables higher-level systems to assess target behavior, identify anomalous motion patterns, or infer potential threats. Furthermore, CAT 025 service and component status reports support Level 4 fusion by enabling adaptive resource management and sensor tasking.

Knowledge of sensor availability, performance degradation, or configuration changes allows fusion systems to dynamically adjust processing strategies and weighting schemes, which is particularly important in distributed passive radar networks.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper reviewed the applicability of the ASTERIX protocol for the exchange of target information originating from passive radar systems. The focus was placed on ASTERIX Categories 015 and 016, which were specifically introduced to support independent non-cooperative surveillance and multistatic sensing configurations. Through the analysis of a generic passive radar architecture and the identification of the information required for effective data fusion, ASTERIX was shown to provide a comprehensive and flexible framework for both intra- and inter-system information exchange.

A detailed mapping between passive radar measurements and ASTERIX data items was established, demonstrating that the protocol can represent both low-level bistatic measurements and higher-level target information, including uncertainty and classification data. While certain quantities, such as carrier wavelength and bistatic velocity resolution, are not explicitly supported by standardized data items, the use of Special Purpose Fields offers a controlled extensibility mechanism when required. Future revisions of the standard should include data items to cover the aforementioned quantities and, in addition, focus on the inclusion of more receiver and transmitter information in a standardized manner. Those should include details such as antenna radiation patterns, effective radiated power, modulation type, etc., to support performance prediction and passive radar location planning. This can be achieved by either extending category 016 messages or defining appropriate database structures that can be indexed by the receiver and transmitter identifiers already present in category 016 messages.

Overall, ASTERIX was found to be well suited as a standardized communication interface for passive radar systems, facilitating integration with heterogeneous sensors and legacy surveillance infrastructures. The required data rate for its application is well within the capabilities of current communication technologies, and can be readily be applied.

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